

Sexualised Corruption in High-Income Democracies: Sub-National Evidence from the European Union

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Abstract

This article examines whether sexualised corruption – the abuse of public power to obtain sexual favours – emerges under the same opportunity structures as petty corruption in advanced democracies. Drawing on representative data from 40,663 respondents from the 2023 Global Corruption Barometer–European Union, we construct regionally disaggregated measures of sexualised corruption across all 27 member states. Our analysis shows that regional prevalence of petty corruption predicts sexualised corruption, but the relationship is conditional: it is strongest in affluent regions and in countries with lower overall corruption and greater gender equality, while in poorer or more corrupt settings sexualised corruption is elevated regardless of petty corruption levels. By contrast, petty corruption does not predict perceptions, which are concentrated in urban and educated regions even as experiences cluster in deprived areas. These findings indicate that rising corruption can inflict severe harms on women, even in countries relatively advanced in combating corruption and promoting gender equality.

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Introduction

Sexualised corruption refers to the abuse of public power to obtain sexual favours – effectively, the use of sex as currency in a corrupt exchange.¹ It occurs when a public official or representative demands sexual acts or favours instead of, or alongside, monetary bribes in return for services, jobs, grades, or other benefits under their control. While the phenomenon has long been documented in the Global South, evidence from high-income democracies remains sparse. Existing cross-national studies suggest that sexualised corruption is more common where established forms of corruption are widespread (Aja-Eke et al. 2025) but cannot establish whether this association holds once national institutions are accounted for, nor can they reveal how sexualised corruption varies within democracies where strong formal rules coexist with pockets of everyday abuse.

This focus on low- and middle-income settings also creates a blind spot. If sexualised corruption is only investigated where corruption is already pervasive, it risks being miscast as a pathology of weak or authoritarian states rather than a systemic variant of corruption. Without systematic study in high-income democracies, the problem appears geographically bounded, when in fact it may emerge wherever officials enjoy discretion and impunity. Our study addresses this imbalance through a subnational analysis of the European Union. Drawing on more than 40,000 GCB-EU interviews, we construct EU-wide, regionally disaggregated measures of sexualised corruption and embed them in models with country fixed effects. This design isolates the local component of sexualised corruption while holding national frameworks constant, allowing us to evaluate whether it emerges from the same opportunity

¹ We use sexualised corruption rather than sexual corruption to avoid the moralistic overtones the latter can carry in English and to match the wording now common in policy guidance from bodies such as Transparency International and the UNCAC Coalition.

structures as routine corruption. In doing so, we also treat the incidence of petty bribery as a reasonable proxy for overall corruption levels, given its well-established association with the broader incidence of corrupt practices.

The results show that the relationship between corruption and sexualised corruption is real but conditional. Bribery prevalence predicts higher rates of sexualised corruption in relatively affluent regions and in countries with stronger institutional performance on corruption and gender equality. By contrast, in poorer or more corrupt contexts sexualised corruption is elevated across the board, largely independent of bribery levels. This dual pattern highlights that while sexualised corruption shares common roots with petty bribery, its manifestation is shaped by local affluence and national institutional environments. It also shows how rising corruption can inflict severe harms on women even in countries that are relatively advanced in combating corruption and promoting gender equality.

We also find that perceptions diverge from experiences. Awareness of sexualised corruption is higher in more urban and educated regions, even though actual prevalence is concentrated in deprived areas. Our index of petty bribery does not predict perceptions of sexualised corruption. This gap suggests that reporting norms and social visibility do not necessarily align with underlying exposure. Together, these results qualify the “shared opportunity structure” hypothesis: sexualised corruption is not simply a uniform by-product of other forms of corruption, but a conditional variant whose incidence depends on both socio-economic vulnerability and institutional context.

The rest of the article is organised in five parts. Section 2 clarifies key terminology, tracing the shift from sextortion to the more inclusive concept of sexualised corruption. It explains why

this change is necessary for analytical precision, measurement, and effective legal and policy responses. Section 3 develops the shared-opportunity-structure hypothesis, arguing that sexualised corruption emerges under the same institutional conditions that permit routine bribery, and outlining the mechanisms that shape when and where sex becomes a substitute for money in corrupt exchanges. Section 4 describes the data, variables, and research design. Section 5 presents the empirical results. Section 6 concludes with reflections on theory, policy, and future research.

From Sextortion to Sexualised Corruption: Definitions and Challenges

In recent years, a growing body of scholarship has highlighted a form of corruption where sex or sexual access, rather than money, is demanded or exchanged by public officials in positions of power. This behaviour, while often prosecuted under sexual violence or harassment statutes, clearly resembles classic corruption: an abuse of public authority for personal gain. To describe this phenomenon, the International Association of Women Judges (IAWJ) introduced the term sextortion in 2008, defining it as a form of corruption in which sex, not money, is the currency of the bribe or extortion (Eldén *et al.* 2020). The concept gained traction quickly, particularly in legal and development circles seeking to expose forms of abuse that had long gone unaddressed in institutional settings (Transparency International 2020; International Bar Association 2019).

Yet despite its early usefulness, the term sextortion presents several limitations. First, it overlaps with a separate and growing area of concern – namely, online image-based blackmail – leading to confusion in both academic and policy discussions. Second, the suffix “-extortion”

implies a threat-based dynamic that does not capture the full range of exchanges in which sexualised corruption can occur. In many cases, sexual acts are not extracted through overt threats, but are instead offered, expected, or normalised within institutional cultures where access to jobs, grades, permits, or services is routinely mediated through gendered power imbalances. The narrow framing of sextortion around explicit coercion thus risks excluding other exploitative but less visibly coercive practices from empirical analysis and legal remedy.

There is growing recognition that the definitional and operational challenges associated with the term sextortion call for a broader, more analytically precise concept. The term sexualised corruption – or, in some sources, sexual corruption – has emerged as a more inclusive alternative (Bjarnegård *et al.* 2024). This terminology refocuses attention on the corrupt transaction itself, identifying the abuse of office for private sexual gain as the central feature, regardless of whether the sexual favour is demanded, offered, or informally expected. Rather than defining the problem solely in terms of extortion, it captures a wider spectrum of corrupt practices where sexual gratification functions as the illicit benefit. In doing so, it aligns the phenomenon more closely with conventional definitions of corruption and reduces ambiguity about what type of behaviour is under discussion.

The shift from sextortion to sexualised corruption also helps resolve the confusion created by overlapping legal and enforcement frameworks. Whereas sextortion is sometimes treated as a cybercrime perpetrated by private individuals, sexualised corruption situates the abuse clearly within the domain of public integrity, emphasising the role of power and position. This makes it easier to locate the phenomenon within anti-corruption strategies and legal frameworks, rather than relegating it to areas of law that may not adequately capture the nature of the abuse.

Another advantage of the term sexualised corruption is that it better reflects the gendered and structural nature of these exchanges (UNCAC Coalition 2023). Scholars have shown that these practices disproportionately affect women, LGBTQ+ persons, and individuals from socio-economically marginalised groups who are more likely to depend on officials for access to public goods and services (Abut 2022). By situating the problem within the broader context of corruption, rather than isolating it as a distinct form of sexual violence, this approach helps expose how gender hierarchies are reproduced through institutionalised abuse.

However, there are several obstacles to mainstreaming this broader terminology. One of the most significant is legal: many anti-corruption statutes define undue advantage in financial terms, leaving sexual payments in a legal grey area (Transparency International 2020). Prosecutors may try to apply either sexual offence laws or general corruption laws, but in practice both approaches face limitations. The evidentiary burden is also substantial. Unlike monetary bribes, sexualised corruption often leaves little trace and is rarely documented in ways that can be used in court. Victims often hesitate to report such abuse due to stigma, fear of retaliation, or a lack of faith in the integrity of reporting channels – particularly when the perpetrator is embedded in the very institution meant to offer protection.

A further challenge is that official data on corruption seldom disaggregates by type of benefit received, and gender-based violence statistics rarely include information about the power dynamics or institutional settings in which sexual abuse occurs (Kirya 2024). As a result, sexualised corruption remains largely invisible in administrative data and national integrity frameworks. This lack of visibility, in turn, hampers the development of effective policy responses.

Finally, the international landscape remains fragmented in its use of terminology. Various actors refer to “sextortion,” “sexual extortion,” “sexualised corruption,” and “gendered corruption,” often without clearly defining the scope of each term. While there are signs of convergence – such as the 2023 UNCAC Resolution 10/10, which recognises sexual demands as a form of corruption – national implementation remains inconsistent (UNCAC Coalition 2025).

In this context, the move toward a more inclusive and analytically grounded term such as sexualised corruption represents a constructive step. It offers conceptual clarity, acknowledges the full spectrum of abuse, and creates space for a more effective legal and policy response. Yet this terminological shift must be matched by concrete reforms: legislative changes to recognise non-pecuniary forms of bribery, improved data collection methods, and reporting systems that are accessible and safe for victims. Without such measures, the problem will remain hidden in plain sight, shielded by institutional silences and conceptual ambiguity.

The Shared Opportunity Structure Hypothesis

The starting point for our analysis is the idea that sexualised corruption is not an anomaly but a variant of corruption that arises under familiar conditions. Where institutional arrangements allow officials to exchange discretion for money, they may also exchange it for sex. In this view, sexualised corruption and bribery share a common opportunity structure: discretionary authority combined with weak accountability. The form of payment – pecuniary or sexual – depends on what can most easily be extracted from those seeking services or benefits (Lindberg and Stensöta 2018; Bjarnegård et al. 2024).

At a baseline, this reasoning suggests a positive correlation between bribery and sexualised corruption across jurisdictions. Officials who can demand money without sanction may just as

readily demand sex. A growing body of evidence supports this expectation. Aja-Eke et al. (2025), analysing cross country data from the 2019–22 Global Corruption Barometer surveys, find that countries that perform worse on the Corruption Perceptions Index are countries in which more people report sexualised corruption, controlling for regime type, press freedom, income, and women’s parliamentary representation. Scholars like Bjarnegård et al. (2024) argue that understanding sexual corruption requires tools from gender-based violence research alongside classic corruption frameworks. In positioning sextortion within corruption studies, researchers are effectively building a more intersectional approach – one that recognizes how corruption can exploit gender vulnerabilities and how patriarchal power dynamics can facilitate corruption.

Case study evidence supports these points: village chiefs in Malawi who extracted informal payments from applicants often substituted or supplemented them with sexual demands, particularly when female claimants were cash-poor (Basel Institute 2021), while officials along North African migration routes demanded both money and sex – the “double price” – depending on what migrants could provide (Transparency International 2020). These examples highlight the fungibility of corrupt currencies in environments where oversight is weak and gatekeepers operate with impunity.

Yet there are reasons to expect this relationship to be conditional rather than uniform. Local socio-economic conditions shape what resources citizens can offer. In poorer regions, cash may be scarce, making sexual access a more available currency; in better-off regions, officials may treat sex as an additional or complementary benefit to monetary bribes. National institutions also condition both opportunity and impunity. Where overall corruption is high or gender inequality entrenched, sexualised corruption may be elevated regardless of local bribery levels.

Conversely, in countries with stronger integrity frameworks or more gender-equal norms, local variation in bribery may be a sharper indicator of opportunities for sexual exploitation.

This perspective shows the value of examining sexualised corruption in advanced democracies. Without systematic analysis in high-income and democratic settings, the phenomenon risks being cast as largely confined to the Global South or to fragile states. Doing so gives the misleading impression that strong formal institutions eliminate the problem, when in fact sexualised corruption can persist in advanced democracies, though its manifestation is conditioned by local opportunity structures and national institutional contexts.

Indeed, three mechanisms help explain why the bribery–sexualised corruption relationship may weaken in higher-income democracies. First, digitisation reduces the face-to-face interactions that sexualised corruption typically requires: the move to online procurement or licensing, for example, narrows the channels where sex-for-favours exchanges can occur. Second, legal reform shifts the cost–benefit calculation. Jurisdictions that expand bribery statutes to include “any undue advantage” – explicitly covering sexual services – increase the expected sanction risk. Third, the diffusion of #MeToo norms raises reputational costs, making sexual demands more visible and less “safe” than pecuniary rents. These mechanisms do not eliminate sexualised corruption, but they alter the calculus, potentially attenuating its correlation with bribery in more rule-bound settings.

Still, opportunity and impunity remain elastic. Sexualised corruption resurfaces in sectors where oversight is limited, rules are discretionary, or protections are ineffective. Education systems, for example, offer opportunities where grades, recommendations, or university entry

can be traded for sex (“sex-for-grades” scandals have emerged across regions).² Local policing and border control involve interactions marked by discretion and high vulnerability. Humanitarian aid and refugee camps illustrate the phenomenon of “survival sex,” where access to food or shelter is mediated by officials or contractors operating with little monitoring.³ These cases show how pockets of high opportunity and impunity persist within otherwise robust institutional environments.

Measurement challenges further complicate analysis. Victims may hesitate to report sexualised corruption due to stigma, fear of retaliation, or confusion over legal definitions. In some legal codes, both bribe-giver and bribe-taker can be criminalised, leading victims to believe they have committed an offence. Unlike monetary bribes, sexualised corruption often leaves little trace and is rarely documented in administrative records. The recent inclusion of sexual corruption questions in major survey instruments represents a breakthrough, but such surveys still depend on respondents recognising and labelling their experience as corruption. As Aja-Eke et al. (2025) note, in highly corrupt environments high incidence often coincides with low perceived prevalence, because such exchanges are normalised. This perception–experience gap points to the need for new measures and helps explain why awareness is concentrated in urban or educated regions even when prevalence is higher elsewhere.

² For example, in the United Kingdom, Jones (2021) reports the OIA ordered a university to compensate a student £5,000 after their dissertation supervisor offered higher grades in exchange for sexual activity. Research in higher education has begun to explore “sex-for-grades” dynamics, noting how discourses of gender, sex, and power circulate in ways that both constrain and shape the agency of female students (Clarke 2022).

³ In another relevant study, Bicker Caarten et al. (2022) conducted a study on migrants’ experiences of sextortion during journeys to South Africa . Through interviews with experts and collected testimonies, they found that irregular female migrants are the most vulnerable to sexual extortion by officials (such as border agents, police, or immigration officers). Further research has examined sextortion as a violation of human rights and as an obstacle to sustainable development (Eldén, Å., et al. 2020).

Two scope conditions are worth emphasising. First, the absence of sexualised corruption in a given setting does not necessarily signal integrity: it may simply reflect that other rents – cash, contracts, or favours – are safer or more rewarding. Second, gender composition alone is not a reliable constraint. At a country level, neither women’s legislative representation nor female labour-force participation significantly reduces sexualised corruption once overall corruption levels are taken into account (Aja-Eke et al. 2025). More important are effective channels for victim voice, such as ombuds offices, whistleblower protections, or trusted complaint mechanisms (Kubbe and Merkle 2025), which reduce impunity even where opportunities persist.

From this literature and logic follow three expectations. First, sexualised corruption should be more prevalent in socio-economically deprived areas, but the incremental effect of bribery exposure may be stronger in more affluent regions where baseline levels are lower. Second, the strength of the bribery–sexualised corruption association should vary with national context: it may be sharpest in less corrupt and more gender-equal countries, and weaker where sexual exploitation and bribery are deeply embedded. Third, perceptions need not align with experiences. Reporting norms, education, and urbanisation may amplify perceived prevalence in some regions while concealing abuse in others.

This reformulated hypothesis thus situates sexualised corruption firmly within mainstream corruption research while recognising its conditional character. It integrates comparative survey evidence (Aja-Eke et al. 2025), conceptual advances in defining sexualised corruption (Bjarnegård et al. 2024), and sectoral case studies (Basel Institute 2021; Transparency International 2020). The empirical analysis that follows tests these propositions using regionally disaggregated data from across the European Union.

Data and Measurement

Our empirical analysis draws on the 2023 wave of the *Global Corruption Barometer – European Union* (GCB-EU), a representative household survey conducted in all twenty-seven EU member states between April and July 2023. The usable sample comprises 40,663 individuals. Each interview is geo-referenced to a NUTS 2 unit, which is nested within a NUTS 1 region and member state.

Sexual corruption prevalence is measured using item Q17B: “In the last twelve months, did a public official ask you – or someone you know personally – for a sexual favour in exchange for a service?” We construct a binary indicator at the individual level (1 = yes, 0 = no), and then aggregate to the NUTS 1 level.. Monetary bribery is drawn from item BRIBETOTFIN, which asks whether the respondent paid a bribe – defined as money or a gift – to a public official in the past year. We construct a binary variable at the individual level and aggregate it to the NUTS 1 scale in the same manner as the sexualised corruption measure.

To address potential confounding, we include the regional means of five demographic and socio-economic characteristics commonly used in corruption research: the proportion of respondents who are female; mean age; mean position on a six-point household income ladder where higher values indicate greater deprivation; mean educational attainment (using a harmonised six-point ISCED scale); and the share residing in medium or large urban areas. Because national level institutions and reporting norms may influence both corruption and disclosure, all models include a full set of country fixed effects.

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for the variables used. We have data for 89 NUTS1 regions. In the average EU NUTS1 region, 7.9% of people report that they or someone they know have been the victim of sexualised corruption. This exceeds the average direct exposure to petty bribery of 5.3%. While this may seem implausible, recall that the latter question focuses on the respondent's direct experiences whereas the former allows respondents to draw on indirect experiences.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	(1)			
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Sextortion prevalence	0.079	0.037	0.020	0.188
Bribery prevalence	0.053	0.042	0.000	0.171
Share female	1.465	0.061	1.260	1.592
Mean age	52.092	3.552	43.490	60.060
Household income (1–6)	1.806	0.367	1.293	2.767
Education (ISCED 1–6)	1.389	0.102	1.153	1.708
Share urban	0.676	0.138	0.394	0.997
Observations	89			

Results

Table 2 reports OLS estimates of sexualised corruption prevalence across the 89 NUTS-1 regions of the European Union. The dependent variable (SC) is the share of respondents who report that they – or someone they know – were asked for sexual favours by a public official in the previous year. Regional values range from 2.0 % to 18.8 % (mean = 7.9 %, s.d. = 3.7). The key explanatory variable is the regional prevalence of monetary bribery, measured as the share of residents who paid money or a gift to a public official; this variable ranges from 0 to 17.2 % (mean = 5.3 %, s.d. = 4.2).

$$SC_r = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Bribery}_r + \mathbf{X}'_r \boldsymbol{\beta}_2 + \gamma_c + \varepsilon_r$$

where r indexes regions and y_c are EU member state fixed effects. The model (column 7) explains 85 % of the cross regional variation in sexualised corruption. The country fixed effects are jointly significant, indicating substantial national heterogeneity once regional covariates are held constant.⁴

Table 2 reports the core association between petty bribery exposure (*Bribery*) and sexualised corruption. Across specifications, the coefficient on *Bribery* is positive and statistically detectable; in the fully adjusted model (col. 7) a one-percentage-point rise in bribery prevalence is associated with a 0.373-point increase in sexualised corruption. Among controls, deprivation is a consistent correlate: because the income ladder is coded so that higher values indicate lower household income, the positive coefficient on *Income* (0.075, s.e. = 0.026, $p < 0.01$, col. 7) implies higher sexualised corruption in more deprived regions. Age is negative and statistically significant in a pared-down specification but not in the full model; education is positive in some specifications but insignificant once all controls are included; the regional female share and urbanisation are not meaningfully related to the outcome once country effects are held constant. Taken together, Table 2 points to a strong empirical link between routine corruption and sexualised corruption within countries, alongside a baseline gradient with material hardship.

⁴ Several Baltic and southern member states – Latvia, Lithuania, Portugal and Hungary – exhibit markedly lower sexualised corruption prevalence than the omitted reference country, whereas Luxembourg is the only state with a (statistically insignificant) positive deviation. These residual differences point to institutional or cultural factors – legal definitions of sexual corruption, complaint mechanisms, gender norms – that are not captured by the present data.

Table 2. Determinants of Sexualised Corruption in the EU at the Regional Level

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Bribery	0.472*	0.427*	0.341*	0.478*	0.471**	0.462*	0.373*
	(0.239)	(0.224)	(0.201)	(0.246)	(0.223)	(0.237)	(0.186)
Female		-0.078					-0.059
		(0.054)					(0.047)
Age			-0.004***				-0.002
			(0.001)				(0.002)
Income				0.060**			0.075***
				(0.026)			(0.026)
Education					0.089**		0.089
					(0.034)		(0.081)
Urban						0.026	-0.008
						(0.022)	(0.032)
Constant	0.071***	0.110***	0.275***	-0.022	-0.044	0.056**	-0.010
	(0.023)	(0.033)	(0.067)	(0.043)	(0.047)	(0.026)	(0.200)
Observations	89	89	89	89	89	89	89
R-squared	0.791	0.798	0.823	0.811	0.808	0.797	0.855

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 3 turns to perceptions of sexualised corruption as dependent variable. Here, *Bribery* is negative and statistically indistinguishable from zero across all specifications (e.g., -0.801 , s.e. = 0.627 , col. 7), despite very high R^2 once country effects are included (0.945 – 0.963). Instead, perceptions correlate with socio-economic and settlement characteristics: more urban and more educated regions report higher perceived sexualised corruption (see coefficients on *Urban* and *Education* in the single-control model), while perceptions are lower in more deprived places (*Income*, col. 7). The divergence from Table 2 suggests that perceived sexualised corruption reflects awareness and reporting environments rather than the within-country distribution of experiences.

Table 3. Dependent Variable: Sexualised Corruption Perceptions

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Bribery	-0.697 (0.752)	-0.789 (0.752)	-0.827 (0.766)	-0.728 (0.631)	-0.702 (0.701)	-0.779 (0.744)	-0.801 (0.627)
Female		-0.157 (0.207)					-0.168 (0.191)
Age			-0.004 (0.005)				0.002 (0.005)
Income				-0.321*** (0.101)			-0.274** (0.108)
Education					0.442*** (0.098)		0.166 (0.200)
Urban						0.203*** (0.064)	0.150* (0.080)
Constant	3.647*** (0.055)	3.727*** (0.123)	3.849*** (0.290)	4.142*** (0.172)	3.073*** (0.142)	3.533*** (0.060)	3.726*** (0.494)
Observations	89	89	89	89	89	89	89
R-squared	0.945	0.945	0.945	0.956	0.953	0.952	0.963

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The interaction between bribery and deprivation is substantively informative. Figure 1 plots the marginal effect of Bribery on sexualised corruption across the deprivation index (*Income*). The slope is clearly positive in relatively better-off regions and attenuates toward zero as deprivation rises. In other words, bribery exposure *amplifies* sexualised corruption where deprivation is lower, while in poorer regions the baseline is already high and the incremental effect of bribery prevalence is small. For reference, mean sexualised corruption is roughly 6.5 % in the better-off half (*Income* > 1.8) versus about 9 % in the more deprived half (*Income* < 1.8).

Figure 1 Marginal Effect of Bribery Incidence on Sexualised Corruption across the Deprivation Index

Table 4 examines whether the bribery–sexualised corruption link depends on national context. Splitting the sample by the 2023 CPI (countries below the EU average are labelled “more corrupt”), the bribery coefficient is small and imprecise in more-corrupt countries (0.225, s.e. = 0.218, col. 1) but sizeable and statistically significant in less-corrupt countries (0.554, s.e. = 0.275, $p < 0.10$, col. 2). A similar pattern emerges when splitting by the EU Gender Equality Index: in less gender-equal countries, the bribery slope is modest and imprecise (0.264, s.e. = 0.246, col. 3), whereas in more gender-equal countries it is larger and significant (0.540, s.e. = 0.247, $p < 0.05$, col. 4). In both sets of splits, deprivation remains a strong positive predictor of sexualised corruption, with a larger and more precisely estimated coefficient in more-corrupt countries (e.g., 0.119, s.e. = 0.028, $p < 0.01$, col. 1) and a smaller, marginally significant coefficient in less-corrupt countries (0.073, s.e. = 0.041, $p < 0.10$, col. 2). Deprivation is most clearly a risk factor for sexualised corruption in contexts of high corruption. The regional female share is slightly negative in the less-corrupt and more-equal subsamples, though the

magnitudes are small. *Urban* is weakly negative in more-corrupt countries and near zero elsewhere. These patterns indicate that where national institutions already deliver low overall corruption or higher gender equality, local bribery exposure is a sharper signal of the opportunity structures that also facilitate sexualised corruption; where corruption or gender inequality is broadly higher, sexualised corruption is elevated across the board and less tightly coupled to cross-regional variation in petty bribery.

Table 4. Sexualised Corruption and National Context

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Sample	More Corrupt Countries	Less Corrupt Countries	Less Gender Equal Countries	More Gender Equal Countries
Bribery	0.225 (0.218)	0.554* (0.275)	0.264 (0.246)	0.540** (0.247)
Female	0.022 (0.061)	-0.111* (0.060)	0.012 (0.083)	-0.109* (0.054)
Age	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)
Income	0.119*** (0.028)	0.073* (0.041)	0.128*** (0.036)	0.091*** (0.022)
Education	0.337*** (0.096)	-0.019 (0.094)	0.404*** (0.132)	-0.034 (0.084)
Urban	-0.129* (0.064)	0.029 (0.033)	-0.161 (0.098)	0.030 (0.030)
Constant	-0.438* (0.236)	0.121 (0.218)	-0.586** (0.272)	0.131 (0.202)
Observations	43	46	37	52
R-squared	0.926	0.742	0.939	0.744

Robust standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Bringing the results together, four points stand out. First, at the regional level, sexualised corruption moves closely with petty bribery within countries, even after adjusting for demographics, urban structure, and country effects (Table 2). Second, perceptions do not track experiences: they are more common in urban, better-educated, and less deprived regions and are not explained by bribery prevalence (Table 3). Third, material hardship shapes both levels

and gradients: sexualised corruption is higher in poorer regions, yet the *marginal* effect of bribery is strongest in better-off areas (Figure 1). Fourth, national context conditions the local link: the bribery–sexualised corruption association is clearest in countries with lower overall corruption and higher gender equality, while deprivation exerts a robust positive association everywhere and especially in more-corrupt states (Table 4). Substantively, these findings situate sexualised corruption within mainstream corruption processes while clarifying that experiences, perceptions, and opportunity structures need not align. They also suggest a practical implication: in relatively affluent regions and in national settings that have made headway on overall corruption and gender equality, spikes in petty bribery are likely to coincide with higher risk of sexual exploitation by officials, whereas in poorer regions and more-corrupt states, elevated risk is more structural and less sensitive to cross-regional variation in bribery exposure.

Conclusion

This article set out to test a straightforward proposition: if public officials have opportunities to trade their discretion for money, they will also be able to trade it for sex. Drawing on more than 40,000 interviews from the 2023 Global Corruption Barometer–European Union – the first systematic measurement of sexualised corruption inside advanced democracies – we provide the most fine-grained evidence to date on the geography of sexualised corruption. The results qualify the “shared opportunity structure” hypothesis rather than simply confirming it. Five broad conclusions follow.

First, sexualised corruption is endemic but unevenly distributed. Reported prevalence varies almost ten-fold across EU regions, clustering where routine bribery is also more common.

Regional models explain over four-fifths of that variation, and the bribery coefficient remains positive across specifications. Sexualised corruption is therefore neither anecdotal nor detached from mainstream corruption processes. It emerges from the same opportunity structures that sustain petty graft.

Second, deprivation raises baseline exposure, but bribery matters more in better-off regions. Regions with higher reported financial hardship show higher rates of sexualised corruption, even after accounting for national context. Yet the marginal effect of bribery prevalence is strongest in relatively affluent areas. This conditionality complicates the idea that sexualised corruption flourishes only in poor societies or weak states. Even within high-capacity EU democracies, economic hardship sustains abuse, but the predictive value of bribery exposure is clearest where deprivation is less acute and opportunities for discretionary exchange are more differentiated.

Third, experiences and perceptions diverge. While sexualised corruption is more common in deprived areas, perceptions of sexual corruption are higher in more urban and educated regions. Awareness appears shaped less by prevalence than by visibility and reporting norms. This perception–experience gap echoes prior research showing that sexualised corruption can be normalised in highly corrupt environments, rendering it less likely to be recognised as abuse. Our findings underscore that perception indicators should not be treated as straightforward proxies for incidence.

Fourth, national context conditions but does not erase local dynamics. Country fixed effects are jointly significant, confirming that legal definitions, enforcement practices, and gender norms shape overall levels of sexualised corruption. Yet the bribery–sexualised corruption link

persists within countries, even under a shared legal umbrella. Notably, the association is strongest in less corrupt and more gender-equal states, whereas in more corrupt or less gender-equal contexts, sexualised corruption is already elevated across the board. This suggests that as formal institutions constrain corruption, bribery becomes a sharper signal of the opportunity structures that also permit sexual abuse.

Fifth, law and enforcement have not kept pace with the problem. In many EU member states, corruption statutes continue to define undue advantage in narrowly financial terms, leaving sexualised corruption in a legal grey zone. Victims are often directed toward harassment or assault provisions that fail to capture the corrupt nature of the exchange. At the EU level, there is still no systematic recognition of sexualised corruption as a corruption offence, despite growing international attention, such as the UNCAC Coalition's calls for reform and Resolution 10/10 adopted at the 2023 Conference of States Parties. Reviews of national legal frameworks (Transparency International 2020; UNCAC Coalition 2023, 2025) note that very few countries explicitly treat sexualised corruption as a form of bribery, and those that do often lack enforcement mechanisms. This absence of legal clarity reinforces institutional neglect: without explicit recognition and sanction, reforms that target monetary bribery alone risk displacing extraction into other currencies of abuse.

These findings carry several implications. For research, they place sexualised corruption squarely inside principal-agent models of corruption and suggest that the "currency" of extraction – money, sex, contracts, or votes – should be treated as an endogenous choice shaped by relative risks, payoffs, and institutional environments. Comparative studies that ignore sexualised corruption risk underestimating the welfare costs of graft and misinterpreting how gendered hierarchies shape the abuse of public authority. For policy, the results stress the

importance of integrated integrity systems. Reforms that narrow discretion (e-government portals), raise detection probability (independent complaint mechanisms), and equalise voice (whistleblower hotlines, survivor protections) are likely to suppress both monetary and sexual bribery. Conversely, anticorruption frameworks that criminalise financial graft but leave coercive sex in a legal grey zone merely displace extraction from one medium to another.

Two limitations should be noted. First, our reliance on self-reported victimisation makes the results sensitive to disclosure biases. Although we mitigate this by comparing regions within shared national legal regimes, under-reporting may still mask latent abuse in more conservative or rural areas. Second, the analysis is cross-sectional: we identify correlations, not trajectories. Future research should draw on panel data – ideally combining repeated GCB waves with administrative complaints – to trace how reforms alter the relative costs of monetary and sexual corruption over time.

Despite these caveats, the study demonstrates that sexualised corruption is neither marginal nor idiosyncratic within the European Union. It is a routine, measurable, and therefore governable manifestation of corruption. By illuminating its sub-national characteristics, we provide a foundation for scholars to integrate sexualised corruption into general theories of accountability, and for policymakers to design interventions that confront all currencies of abuse – not just those denominated in cash.

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